

PROPOSED READING INTERVENTION MATERIALS FOR GRADE 8 LEARNERS

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Proposed Reading Intervention Materials for Grade 8 Learners

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Abstract

This research study attempted to develop and evaluate Reading Intervention Materials in English for Grade 8 Learners at San Jose National High School, in the Schools Division of Antipolo, District II-A during the school year 2023-2024. The researcher used the descriptive method of research using a survey questionnaire as the main research instrument. Based on the results, the English experts and English teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Content, Format, and Presentation and Organization as Very Acceptable (VA) with the obtained grand weighted mean ratings of 3.75 and 3.78, respectively and showed no significant difference on their evaluation. More so, the readability level of the selected reading text based on the readability test results using the Flesch Reading Formula in the developed Reading Intervention Materials is under standard level. The selected reading texts are appropriate for Grade 8 students as regards to the reading difficulty. Comments and suggestions were given by the respondents to further improve the learning material.

Keywords: *intervention material, reading, Grade 8*

Introduction

The complexity of modern civilization has increased the need for literacy, particularly in our print-saturated world where people constantly come across situations where they must read a variety of print materials, including operations manuals, complex technical reports, schedules, warning labels, and instructions for numerous procedures. People stay up to date on global concerns by reading books, periodicals, and newspapers on their own.

Reading is essential for education. The secret to opening the door to lifetime learning is to instill a passion of reading in children at a young age. When books are read aloud to children, they provide a source of memorable, enjoyable, and stimulating early experiences. Youngsters who grow up to respect books are more likely to read independently and to do so for the rest of their life. Early reading instruction provides a child with a strong foundation for vocabulary growth, independence, and self-assurance. It fosters children's imagination and social-emotional abilities while assisting them in making sense of both the outside world and other people.

An author and writing teacher Roz Morris (2019), emphasized that "Reading exposes us to other styles, other voices, other forms and other genres of writing importantly, it exposes us to writing that's better than our own and helps us to improve." She also added that "Reading -the good and the bad-inspires you."

Relatively, many people view reading as a lifetime ability that can be applied in both the classroom and in daily life. One essential life skill is reading. Educators believe that it is essential to a child's achievement in school and, in fact, in life. Opportunities for both career success and personal fulfillment will undoubtedly be lost if one cannot read proficiently. But reading is one of the most challenging skills our students need to learn. However, the demand for literacy in this technological society makes this problem even more complicated.

Because of the principal place of reading in modern life, the teachers have a responsibility to ensure that young people learn to read well for them to succeed in education for their future lives.

However, the reading performance of the Filipino learners and the country's standing as regards this matter were put in the spotlight as reflected in different reports on the results of various international assessment. Recently, the Education First (EF), an international education company, announced that the Philippines dropped by seven (7) steps from its 20th standing in 2019. Its fall to 27th rank in international standing against one hundred countries urged stringent assessment of present curricula both in elementary and high school, especially that timelines on the narrowing advantage of Filipino graduates in global language worsen from 2016 when the Philippines spotted 13th, 15th in 2017, and 14th in 2018. The records were significant because of the reading difficulties of Filipinos.

Furthermore, the result of the Program for International Students Assessment (PISA) 2018 showed that there were only 38.36 % of the Filipino student-participants can evaluate simple sentences and 26.74 % can understand literal meaning of sentences or can recognize the main theme of a piece of text. This places the Philippines in the second to the lowest among the OECD participating country. It was also reported that the Philippines is still among the countries with the lowest proficiency in Reading Comprehension, Mathematics and Science among 15-year-old students, according to (PISA) 2022 results (CNN Philippines).

Reading comprehension in the Philippines is low due to several factors. One factor is the limited availability of reading materials, both at home and in schools. Another factor is the inadequacy of reading instruction, which affects students' ability to strong comprehension skills. Additionally, there may be a lack of intervention programs to address weak areas of reading comprehension, such as interpretative, critical and application skills. These factors contribute to the low levels of comprehension in the Philippines.

For the School Year 2022-2023, the reading assessment results revealed that there were 2,689 independent readers, 3,711 instructional readers, 303 were identified as frustration readers and 1 nonreader. For Grade 8, there were 92 students identified under frustration level and 1 nonreader. Relative to this, to ensure that every Filipino child learns to read, the Department of Education has been persistent in implementing a variety of reading programs at all levels of basic education. However, the reading competence and literacy rate continues to plunge as evidenced by the reading assessment done in public schools as reported in San Jose National High School.

These scenarios push the researcher to conduct this study. As a language and reading teacher, she wishes to develop and evaluate reading materials that will enhance their reading and comprehension skills of Grade 8 students under frustration level. She believes that the material that she will be crafting will be of immense help to aid the learners, as well as the teachers, in conducting reading intervention sessions which may lead to their significant development.

Research Questions

This study aimed to address learning competency deficiencies in English 8 thru the development and evaluation of Proposed Reading Intervention Materials for Grade 8 Students at San Jose National High School, in the Schools Division of Antipolo during the School Year 2022-2023. This study attempted to seek answers on the following questions:

1. What are the Top 3 least mastered skills in the four quarterly examination during the School Year 2022-2023 that could be used in developing reading intervention materials for Grade 8 learners under frustration level?
2. What is the evaluation of the English experts and English teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials with respect to the following criteria:
 - 2.1. content;
 - 2.2. format; and
 - 2.3. organization and presentation?
3. Is there any significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents in terms of the above cited criteria?
4. What is the readability level of the selected reading texts based on the Flesch Reading Ease Formula?
5. What comments/suggestions are given by the respondents relative to the improvement of the developed reading intervention materials?

Literature Review

According to Llego (2022), the Philippines' reading proficiency has historically been a source of concern for some educators and policymakers. Numerous studies have been conducted to try to identify the cause of the issue, and different interventions have been implemented to raise student reading proficiency.

In addition, Espejo, et al. (2018) cited that reading, background knowledge is particularly important in the Common Core era. Children will be expected to acquire knowledge through text, both narrative and informative, within predetermined difficulty ranges at each grade level to satisfy the expectations of these new standards. Academic and conceptual language are likely to be more prevalent in informational texts than in other types of writing. Also, reading comprehensively really affects learner's education and his life (Ozdemir, 2020).

Furthermore, Kerubo (2019) searched the connection between reading comprehension techniques and academic achievement. Decoding deficiencies, poor memory, a lack of inferences, and a lack of vocabulary are the causes of comprehension problems. A small number of students had comprehension issues, as seen by their slow reading rate and skipping words and letters. As a result, their performance was just average on the intellectual and comprehension passages. There is a connection between academic achievement and comprehension issues.

Similarly, Bonganciso (2020) asserts that the ability to comprehend and process material is a prerequisite for reading. The ability to comprehend material quickly is essential for reading. When we can "visually process virtually every letter of the text," we can say that we have successfully read.

Basilan (2018) said that reading comprehension has different purposes that change as humans read. These are experiences from external messages set by writers, the reader's purposes, and context-mandated objectives of teachers, curriculum, and culture that affect understanding. He added that there are several activities related to comprehension.

Moreover, Camba (2023) titled Digitized Remedial Instructional Materials in Afro-Asian Literature for Grade 8 Learners. This study was conducted to develop and evaluate remedial instructional materials in Afro-Asian literature for grade 8 learners. The respondents evaluated the developed Digitized Remedial Instructional Materials in Afro-Asian Literature for Grade 8 Learners as Very Acceptable in terms of Content Quality, Instructional Quality, and Technical Quality.

Consequently, Domingo (2023) developed in his study a Supplementary Learning Material in Research for English 10 learners. It was concluded that the developed Supplementary Learning Materials in Research for English 10 learners may be utilized as effective learning materials in teaching lessons in Research for English 10 learners.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized descriptive method of research employing an adapted survey questionnaire as the main instrument to gather necessary data. Bhat (2022) explained that descriptive research is a research method describing the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. The method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demographic segment without focusing on why a particular phenomenon occurs. In other words, it describes the research subject without covering why it happens.

Respondents

The data in this study were gathered from the fifteen (15) English experts and twenty-five (25) teachers of English from the selected schools in Schools Division of Antipolo City. The researcher used purposive sampling technique in choosing the English experts and teachers who served as the respondents of the study. She chooses them from the schools in the SDO Antipolo City because she was given permission to conduct the study in any school in Antipolo City.

Instrument

The study utilized survey-questionnaire as the primary instrument in data gathering. It consisted of criteria on Content, Format on Prints, Illustrations, Design and Layout, Paper and Binding, Size and Weight of Resource and Presentation and Organization. It had two major parts. Part I contained the criteria for evaluating the proposed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Content, Format and Presentation and organization as stated above. The second part was intended for the comments and suggestions of the teacher respondents.

Procedure

The study was undertaken during the school year 2023-202. Permission to conduct the study has been secured from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Antipolo. After the approval of the letter or request, she then proceeded to the different schools and spoke with the School Principals of Antipolo National High School, Dalig National High School, San Isidro National High School, San Jose National High School, and San Roque National High School to administer the survey questionnaire.

After testing the reliability of the selected literary texts for the intervention materials, the researcher personally distributed the reading leaning material and survey questionnaire. Fifteen (15) English experts and twenty-five (25) English teachers were asked to evaluate the developed learning materials in the different schools in Antipolo mentioned above.

After the evaluation, the data gathered was submitted for data analysis by the statistician using the appropriate statistical tools. The data given to the researcher was then analyzed and interpreted. Comments and suggestions have been sought for further improvement of the developed material. The summary of findings, conclusions, and recommendations were also completed.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

The Top Three Least Mastered Competencies Per Quarter Examination During the School Year 2022-2023

Table 1. *Computed Mean and Rank of Least Mastered Competencies Based on the Result of the School's First to Fourth Quarter Examination during the S.Y. 2022-2023*

First Quarter Least Mastered Competencies		Mean	Rank
Determine the meaning of words and expressions that reflect the local culture by noting context clues		51.85	3
Use modal verbs, nouns, and adverbs appropriately.		43.76	2
Identify and use signals that indicate coherence (additive, causative, conditional/concessional, sequential, and clarifying)		39.19	1
Second Quarter Least Mastered Competencies		Mean	Rank
Transcode information from non-linear to linear		60.04	2
Use appropriate grammatical signals or expressions suitable to each pattern of idea development: general to particular, claim and counterclaim, problem-solution, and cause and effect		53.17	1
Predict the gist of the material viewed based on the title, pictures, and excerpt		66.42	3
Third Quarter Least Mastered Competencies		Mean	Rank
Analyze intention of words or expressions used in propaganda techniques		46.21	1
Determine various social, moral, and economic issues discussed in the text listened to		51.41	3
Analyze literature as a mirror to a shared heritage of people with diverse background		48.50	2
Fourth Quarter Least Mastered Competencies		Mean	Rank
Use appropriate grammatical signals or expressions suited to each pattern of idea development		60.64	2
Compose effective paragraph		60.70	3
Develop paragraph that illustrate each text type: narrative, literature, expository, explanatory, factual and personal recount, and persuasive		58.41	1

The least mastered competencies in English 8 in San Jose National High School for the School Year 2022-2023 are the following: for the First Quarter, Identify and use signals that indicate coherence has the least computed mean and placed rank 1; while placing in the second is use modal verbs, nouns and adverbs appropriately. For the Second Quarter, Use appropriate grammatical signals or expressions suitable to each pattern of idea development: general to particular, claim and counterclaim, problem-solution and cause and effect placed rank 1, transcode information from linear to non-linear text placed second and predict the gist of the material viewed based on the title, pictures and excerpt. In the Third Quarter, analyze intention of words or expressions used in propaganda techniques is the least mastered competency while analyze literature as a mirror to a shared heritage of people with diverse background and determine various social, moral, and economic issues discussed in the text listened to as the second and third least mastered competencies respectively. In the Fourth Quarter, develop paragraph that illustrate each text type: narrative, expository, explanatory, factual and personal recount and persuasive has the least computed mean; while use appropriate grammatical signals or expressions suited to each pattern of idea development and compose effective paragraph got the second and third least mastered competencies.

Evaluation of the English Experts and Teachers on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials

Table 2. *Evaluation of the English experts and English teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Content*

<i>In terms of Content</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>		
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1. Content is suitable to the student's level of development	3.80	VA	3.76	VA	
2. Material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended.	3.80	VA	3.72	VA	
3. Material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving, etc.	3.80	VA	3.72	VA	
4. Material is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial and gender biases and prejudices.	3.73	VA	3.72	VA	
5. Material enhances the development of desirable values and traits	3.73	VA	3.80	VA	
6. Material has the potential to arouse interest of target reader	3.80	VA	3.72	VA	
7. Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are of concern	3.53	VA	3.60	VA	
	Average Mean	3.74	VA	3.72	VA
	Overall Average Mean	3.73 – Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of content as Very Acceptable with the obtained average mean of 3.74 and 3.72 respectively, which resulted to an Overall Average Mean of 3.73 with verbal interpretation of Very Acceptable.

The data revealed that the experts and teachers strongly believed that the content is suitable to the student's level of development, the material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended, the material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving, and others.

This result is supported by the study of Mijares (2023) that the supplementary learning materials passed the criterion on content. It also suggests that the learning materials must be carefully assessed following the content criterion provided by the DepEd so it can be used as instructional material to improve Science teaching, facilitate the learning process, and most importantly, to improve student achievement on least mastered competencies.

Table 3. *Evaluation of the English Experts and English Teachers on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Prints*

<i>In terms of Format</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>		
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	
1. Prints					
Size of letters is appropriate to the intended user	3.93	VA	4.00	VA	
Spaces between letters and words facilitate reading	3.80	VA	3.84	VA	
1.3 Font is easy to read	3.87	VA	4.00	VA	
1.4 Printing is of good quality (i.e., no broken letters, even density, correct alignment, properly placed screen registration)	3.73	VA	3.88	VA	
	Average Mean	3.83	VA	3.93	VA
	Overall Average Mean	3.88 – Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials for Grade 8 Learners in terms of format on prints as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.83 and 3.93, respectively.

The data exposed that the experts and teachers are completely convinced that the size of letters is appropriate to the intended user, spaces between letters and words facilitate reading, font is easy to read, and printing is of good quality.

Similar findings appeared in the study of Yongco & Del Valle (2022) that most of the respondents strongly agree to the statement that the instructional module has proper spaces between words to ease reading.

Table 4. *Evaluation of the English Experts and English Teachers on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in Terms of Format on Illustrations*

<i>In terms of Format</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
2. Illustrations				
2.1 Simple and easily recognizable	3.87	VA	3.84	VA
2.2 Clarify and supplement the text	3.87	VA	3.68	VA
2.3 Properly labelled or captioned. (if applicable)	3.80	VA	3.64	VA
2.4 Realistic/appropriate colors	3.80	VA	3.80	VA
2.5 Attractive and appealing	3.80	VA	3.92	VA
2.6 Culturally relevant	3.67	VA	3.84	VA
Average Mean	3.80	VA	3.79	VA
Overall Average Mean	3.80– Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of format on illustrations as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.80 and 3.79, respectively.

The result implies that the two groups of respondents believe that the developed learning material has followed the correct format on illustrations that are made to be interesting, and illustrations are made related to the text.

The results are in line with the study of Aquino (2018) which he stated that illustrations could attract attention, aid retention, and enhance understanding, or create context.

The validators emphasized that the supplementary learning material is appropriate for learners as it provides comprehensive information with the use of illustrations, audio-visual and digital resources.

Table 5. *Evaluation of the English Experts and English Teachers on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in Terms of Format on Design and Layout*

<i>In terms of Format</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
3. Design and Layout				
3.1 Attractive and pleasing to look at	3.80	VA	3.88	VA
3.2 Simple (i.e. does not distract the attention of the reader)	3.87	VA	3.84	VA
3.3 Adequate illustration in relation to text	3.80	VA	3.64	VA
3.4 Harmonious blending of elements	3.87	VA	3.76	VA
Average Mean	3.83	VA	3.78	VA
Overall Average Mean	3.81 – Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of format on design and layout as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.83 and 3.78, respectively.

The result implies that the two groups of respondents accept the developed learning material and has followed the correct format on design and layout which made the reading experience more interesting and engaging for the reader.

This is similar with Castor (2019), that the format of instructional material makes the lesson more enjoyable. The illustrations are clear and descriptive, and font is readable, paragraphs are not crowded, with airy space that illustrations, pictures, and other drawings are clearly presented.

Table 6. *Evaluation of the English experts and English teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Paper and Binding*

<i>In terms of Format</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
4. Paper and Binding				
4.1 Paper used contributes to easy reading	3.87	VA	3.88	VA
4.2 Durable binding to withstand frequent use	3.60	VA	3.80	VA
Average Mean	3.73	VA	3.84	VA
Overall Average Mean	3.79– Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of format on paper and binding as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.73 and 3.84, respectively.

The result implies that the two groups of respondents strongly agreed that the developed learning material provided the correct

protection and holding of the reading intervention material and allowed it to be accessible to the readers.

The result is similar to the study of Domingo (2023) which stated that the experts and teachers passionately believed that the paper used contributes to pleasurable reading, and durable binding to withstand frequent use of the reading intervention material.

Table 7. *Evaluation of the English experts and English teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Size and Weight of Resource*

<i>In terms of Format</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
5. Size and Weight of Resource				
5.1 Easy to handle	3.80	VA	3.72	VA
5.2 Relatively light	3.87	VA	3.68	VA
Average Mean	3.83	VA	3.70	VA
Overall Average Mean	3.77– Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of format on size and weight of resource as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.83 and 3.70, respectively.

The result implies that the two groups of respondents supported the idea that the developed learning material is suited for the learners to read and allowed them for more enjoyment with the different activities provided in each lesson.

Similarly, Lazo and De Guzman (2021), found out in their study that Usability compositions were traits of the effective utilization of the Intervention Materials.

Table 8. *Evaluation of the English experts and English teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Presentation and Organization*

<i>In terms of Presentation and Organization</i>	<i>Experts</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable	3.80	VA	3.88	VA
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas	3.87	VA	3.84	VA
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader’s likely experience and level of understanding	3.60	VA	3.72	VA
4. Length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader	3.73	VA	3.76	VA
5. Sentences and paragraph structures are varied and interesting to the target reader	3.53	VA	3.84	VA
Average Mean	3.71	VA	3.81	VA
Overall Average Mean	3.76– Very Acceptable			

The English Teachers and Master Teachers evaluated the developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 in terms of presentation and organization as Very Satisfactory with the obtained Average mean of 3.71 and 3.81, respectively.

The result implies that the two groups of respondents fully agreed that the developed learning material has presented and organized the learning activities from simple and engaging activities to more difficult activities to master its most essential learning competencies.

The findings of the present study are in line with the findings of Osido (2023), from which the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the organization and presentation of the developed Quizziz-Assisted Instructional Materials for Mathematics 8 are verbally interpreted as Very Highly Acceptable.

Test of Significant Difference between the Evaluation of Experts and Teachers on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Content*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.72	0.80	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.74			

Since the computed p value of 0.80 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of content. The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of content.

Correspondingly with the findings of Tindugan (2023), that there is no significant difference between the evaluations of the two groups of respondents on the developed Electronic Strategic Intervention Materials in English 9.

Without a doubt, the claim about the understandability of the presented materials is beyond refutation, confirmed by the unanimity of the evidence provided by both groups of participants.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Prints*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.83	0.20	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.93			

Since the computed p value of 0.20 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on prints.

The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on prints. In unison, looking at the findings provided, it is evident that both groups of people did not find it much of a difference scoring the Reading Intervention Materials based on print format for English 9 in terms of anything technical.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format Illustrations*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.80	0.90	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.79			

Since the computed p value of 0.90 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on illustrations.

The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on illustrations. The data indicates that there is unanimity in the perception of how the pictures and drawings in the developed Reading Intervention Materials.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Design and Layout*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.83	0.62	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.78			

Since the computed p value of 0.62 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on design and layout.

The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on design and layout. The data aligns to findings that the experts and teachers generally seem to think alike concerning the appearance or designing and the layout of the developed Reading Intervention Materials.

Table 13. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Paper and Binding*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.73	0.41	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.84			

Since the computed p value of 0.41 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on paper and binding.

The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on paper and binding. Thus, these findings could reflect that the developed Reading Intervention Materials contain technical qualities in harmony with the evaluation of the two group of respondents.

Table 14. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Size and Weight of Resource*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.83	0.30	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.70			

Since the computed p value of 0.30 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of

format on size and weight of resource.

The data imply that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of format on size and weight of resource.

Table 15. *Test of Significant Difference on the Developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of Format on Presentation and Organization*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p. Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experts	3.83	0.30	Failed to reject H ₀	Not Significant
Teachers	3.70			

Since the computed p value of 0.30 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is proven. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the evaluations of experts and teachers on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of presentation and organization.

The data implies that both experts and teachers have the same judgement on the developed Reading Intervention Materials in terms of presentation and organization. Consequently, these findings signify the veracity of the developed Reading Intervention Materials in enhancing the proficiency of learners as assessed by the experts and teacher respondents.

Table 16. *The Reading Readability Level of the Selected Reading Text Based on the Readability Test Results*

<i>Title of Text</i>	<i>Readability Test Result (60-69)</i>	<i>Reading Difficulty</i>	<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Age Range</i>
1. Ramayana	63	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-15
2. Tale of Two Brothers	65	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
3. The Aged Mother	68	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
4. Southeast Asia's Increasing Search for Mental Health Services	61	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-15
5. Tale of Chunhyang	65	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-15
6. The Thief Who Became a Disciple	68	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
7. The Story of Savitri: The True Essence of Love and Friendship	64	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
8. The Wonder Tree	67	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
9. Biography of Rabindranath Tagore	63	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-15
10. Happy Mirror	69	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14
11. The Golden Harvest	68	Standard	Eighth Grade	13-14

The Flesch Reading Ease Formula is used in the readability level of the selected reading text on the developed Reading Intervention Materials for Grade 8. There are eleven (11) literary texts used in this learning material.

The data imply that the selected reading texts are appropriate for Grade 8 students as regards to the reading difficulty which is standard. To use the formula, count the total number of words, sentences and syllables in a given text. These texts are suited for Grade 8 under thirteen (13) to fifteen (15) years old because the score between 60 and 70 is considered acceptable for Grade 8 learners. The stories selected are relevant and interesting to the learner and these literary selections will also help them be engaged and motivated to read.

The study of Lebosada (2019), made use of a document analysis of the areas of difficulties in Reading based on the results of the achievement test. Using the least mastered skills in Reading, the researcher developed an enhancement reading material as the main gathering tool.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Respondents to Further Improve the developed Reading Intervention Materials for Grade 8 Learners

These are the comments and suggestions of the two groups of respondents to further improve the Reading Intervention Materials in Grade 8.

Comments: (a) The material is well-developed. This could be used for the Catch-Up Fridays. (b) The developed learning materials are suitable to the needs of learners to achieve reading skills and will help to enhance learners' thinking skills by answering different activities. (c) Engaging content and clear language make it educational and enjoyable. (d) The proposed reading intervention materials for Grade 8 learners are very helpful for them. Its content is suitable to their needs. (e) The reading intervention material offers a diverse range of texts and engaging activities to improve literacy skills. (f) The material is very commendable, most of the activities are suited to the target subject. The topics will greatly help the learners, indeed the researcher planned well. (g) The reading materials that were used are interesting, relevant, and relatable. The learning activities are arranged sequentially. They also contain HOTS learning tasks. (h) Lessons are well-planned. Used different strategies for the activities. (i) The developed learning material is suitable to the needs of the learners. The content of the material was well crafted. (j) Material is more interactive. (k) Contents and learning objectives are congruent. Lessons, activities, presentations, and format are age appropriate to the target grade level. Illustrations and graphs are recognizable, and examples provided are relevant and relatable to learners. Answer keys are also provided. (l) Objectives are aligned to the given activities. There are various activities that can capture the interest of learners. The material itself is easily comprehensible

and the content and presentations are suitable to the target learners. (m) The materials are very timely for the students. It's good that there are stories/paragraphs for the need of readings as to intervene students in reading and vocabulary. The fonts and styles are also attractive and excellent. Overall, this material is appropriate and outstanding. (n) The material shows instruction-based activities, and the chosen reading text was appropriate to the reading level of the students. Examples were very evident in each topic, relevant, and further explains the objective. (o) The material is appropriate to the learners because it focuses on the least mastered skills of each grading period.

Suggestions: (a) Add more illustrations since the target students are Grade 8 learners. However, the flow of the lesson is easy to follow and could foster individualized/self-learning. (b) Include prompts in the writing part. (c) If readers are identified as frustration readers, shorten the material so they can read it more easily. (d) Use the unfamiliar words in sentences for the students to easily identify the meaning of those words.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study. There were eleven competencies which were considered most difficult and could be addressed in the development of Reading Intervention Materials in improving the reading skills of the students. The developed Reading Intervention Materials in English 8 was found very commendable by the English experts and teacher respondents. The developed Reading Intervention Material may be used to improve the performance of the students in English 8.

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